

Comparing use of nitroglycerine and nifedipine for preterm labour patients

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ABSTRACT

Objective:

The aim of this analysis is to differentiate the results of Nitroglycerin versus Nifedipine to postpone the time of preterm delivery.

Materials and Methods:

200 women with preterm delivery were included in the observation and were divided between two groups via lottery method. Group A was administered Nifedipine and Group B nitroglycerin. Females were observed up till the day of delivery and complications post child birth were duly noted in predesigned Performa. Informed consent was taken from the participants. Non probability purposive sampling was utilized to select the cases. Entry and analysis of the data was done in SPSS (version 10).

Results: Average prolongation of pregnancy in Group A was 41.23 hours \pm 25.11SD. In Group A, among 100 patients; 58(58%) had 2 days prolongation of pregnancy followed by 23(23%) patients who had 1 day prolongation. In Group B out of 100 patients; in 54(54%) days prolongation of pregnancy was observed followed by 17(17%) patients who had 1 day prolongation in pregnancy. In group A, 19(19%) females had more than 2 days prolongation of pregnancy and in group B pregnancy was prolonged in 29(29%) patients for more than 2 days. Difference in prolongation of pregnancy in both the groups was insignificant with p value 0.653. There was a higher rate of complications in Group B. Group A revealed 21% post treatment headache. In Group B, it was 32% of the patients. 18% patients of Group A were admitted in NICU, while 35% in Group B.

Conclusion: Nifedipine is effective for preterm delivery treatment.

Key Words: Nifedipine, preterm delivery, Nitroglycerine.

INTRODUCTION

Preterm labor is a major concern in pregnancy and poses a threat to baby's health and existence. The incidence of preterm birth is around 5-18% among 184 countries (Chang et al. 2013). Annually 15 million preterm births are recorded. 9% of births are affected by the preterm labor in high income countries while 13% of births in middle and low income countries (Simhan & Caritis, 2007). It usually occurs from 20th -37th week of pregnancy and takes place due to the uterine contractions that

results in dilation of crevice prior to full term gestation. Though several kinds of medications have been introduced to avoid preterm labour however we've received mixed results (Flenady et al. 2014). Tocolytic drugs utilized to prevent for preterm labours are magnesium sulfate (MgSO₄), Nifedipine and indomethacin. Nifedipine is safer to use to manage preterm labour (Kashanian, Zamen & Sheikhsari 2014). Nifedipine has been quite effective from preventing preterm births and occurrence of intraventricular hemorrhage, RDS, Necrotizing Enterocolitis (King et al. 2003). The purpose of this study is to compare the effectiveness of Nitroglycerin and Nifedipine induction in females to prolong their gestational age. This is the first local research to be published on this matter. With the help of this study we will be able to establish the role of Nifedipine and Nitroglycerine for prolongation of pregnancy

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted at Obstetrics and Gynaecology Department, Surgimed Hospital, Lahore, starting from 1st February, 2017 till 1st February, 2018. Sample size was 200 (100 per Group). Consecutive (non probability) sampling technique was used. It was a randomized controlled trial study. 200 pregnant females with preterm labour aged 20-40 were present for the study, with cervical dilation of >1cm and effacement >50%. Females with ruptured membrane, and fetal indication for termination were not included. Patient's demographic details, gestational age, contact and an informed consent was taken. Participants were classified in two Groups using the Lottery Method. Patients of Group A were given 29mg Nifedipine. It could be repeated after another 1 hr if needed. Otherwise continuation of 20 mg was given after a 6 hour gap and continued for 48 hours. Group B was administered an abdominal patch of transdermal Nitroglycerin (10mg). If contractions do not cease for another hour additional patch would be applied. New patch was applied after 24 hours, and were not taken out until 12 hours after contractions were ceased. Each patient was followed up after the birth of baby, neonates' admission to NICU and maternal headaches were observed. Data was recorded in a

pro form and was analyzed in SPSS v.10. Frequencies and percentages were determined for categorical variables. Mean \pm SD was estimated for numerical variables like, gestational age, like age parity and gravida. Chi square test was implemented to compare the prolongation and complications of pregnancy in each group. P value of less than 0.05 was considered. Post stratification chi square test was implemented.

RESULTS

Average prolongation of pregnancy in Group A was 41.23 hours \pm 25.11SD. In Group A, among 100 patients; 58(58%) had 2 days prolongation of pregnancy followed by 23(23%) patients who had 1 day prolongation. In Group B out of 100 patients; in 54(54%) days prolongation of pregnancy was observed followed by 17(17%) patients who had 1 day prolongation in pregnancy. In group A, 19(19%) females had more than 2 days prolongation of pregnancy and in group B pregnancy was prolonged in 29(29%) patients for more than 2 days. Difference in prolongation of pregnancy in both the groups was insignificant with p value 0.653. There was a higher rate of complications in Group B. Group A revealed 21% post treatment headache. In Group B, it was 32% of the patients. 18% patients of Group A were admitted in NICU, while 35% in Group B.

DISCUSSION

Premature birth is a major cause of perinatal mortality and morbidity and it causes 70% of perinatal mortality. In low and middle income countries it is a common incidence. Premature birth ranges from 7.4-13.3% in these countries and 8% in high income countries. Chronic lung disease, cerebral palsy, and respiratory distress syndrome and intraventricular haemorrhage, are cause of a preterm birth. Tocolytic medication is considered to be controversial. Conde-Agudelo et al (2011) is

in agreement with those who proposed that calcium channel blocker, like Nifedipine can be administered as a first line therapy for tocolysis. A Cochrane review about calcium channel blockers (CCBs) to treat acute tocolysis in preterm labor stated that when Nifedipine therapy is started, the preterm delivery risk before 34 weeks is decreased within 7 days, and neonatal outcomes are improved. The comparison of Nitroglycerin and Nifedipine by Amorim et al, (2009) revealed the rate of preterm labour within 48 hours of their administration was 15.4% and 12.5% respectively. A study by Dhawle et al., (2013) revealed that after 48 hours labour prolongation was notably higher in the Nifedipine arm 88.4% as compared to Nitroglycerin 68.3%. Nifedipine helped prolong pregnancy for 7 days in 72.1% and 14 days in 62.8% cases. This is not different when compared with NTG which prolonged pregnancy for 7 days in 65.9% and for 14 days in 58.6% cases. Child delivery was delayed for 2 days by Nifedipine in 76.6% and by NTG in 75.3%, which was not significantly different. Prolongation in pregnancy in this study was 36.93 Hour \pm 23.64 in the NTG group against 40.09 hours \pm 26.26 in the Nifedipine arm. It is the same as the conclusion of Papatsonis et al (1997) 39.2% in Nifedipine arm as compared to 22.1% in Ritodrine arm & Lees et al (1999) 35.8% in NTG as compared to Ritodrine 36.9%.

CONCLUSION

We have arrive at a conclusion the oral Nifedipine effectively delayed the pregnancy for further 48 hours as compared to the transdermal NTG. Tocolysis failed with application of transdermal NTG patch. Nitroglycerin has higher rate of complication than Nifedipine in terms of post treatment headache and admissions of neonates to ICU.

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